

Acceptor behavior of organotin(IV)-2,4-dinitrophenoxides with nitrogen donors

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The tri- and di-organotin(IV)-2,4-dinitrophenoxides of the type $[R_3Sn(OC_6H_3(NO_2)_2-2,4)]$ and $[Bu_2^R SnCl_{2-x}(OC_6H_3(NO_2)_2-2,4)_x]$ ($R = Ph$ and Me ; $x = 1$ and 2) react with nitrogenous donors such as cyanopyridines (CNPy), 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) to yield 1 : 1 adducts. The donor sites of the ligands have been inferred and tentative stereochemistry is assigned in each case.

Tin(IV) compounds containing nitrogen donors possess antitumor activities^{1,2}. Among nitrogen donors, though a rich and varied coordination chemistry of cyanopyridines³ has been found, yet no attempt seems to have been made on their coordination tendency towards organotin aryloxides. Owing to these interesting observations and as part of a continuing study of new organotin(IV) complexes derived from 2,4-dinitrophenol, the present paper describes the acceptor behavior of the title complexes towards some nitrogenous ligands, viz. cyanopyridines, 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline.

Results and Discussion

The formation of nitrogen base adducts of organotin(IV)-2,4-dinitrophenoxides can be depicted as

($R = Ph$ and Me ; $B = 3$ - and 4 -cyanopyridines, bipy and phen).

The analytical data of the isolated complexes are in agreement with their 1 : 1 stoichiometric formulations (Table 1). The complexes are coloured crystalline solids and are soluble in common organic solvents. The molar conductance values suggest their non-ionic nature. The molecular weight data are suggestive of their monomeric character.

In the IR spectra of 3- and 4-cyanopyridine adducts,

bands due to ν_{C-N} mode at around 2232 and 2242 cm^{-1} , compared to those of the free bases (2225 and 2240 cm^{-1} , respectively) suggested that the nitrile nitrogen of the bases do not participate in coordination. On the other hand, the characteristic four principal bands due to $C\equiv C$ and $C\equiv N$ stretch at 1592–1410 cm^{-1} in uncoordinated bases shifted to higher wavenumber in their complexes, suggesting the coordination through ring nitrogen in consonance with the earlier observations⁴ of pyridine complexes. In addition, the two low frequency bands known to appear at 965 and 1000 cm^{-1} in 3-cyanopyridine and at 985 and 1078 cm^{-1} in 4-cyanopyridine also appeared at higher frequencies on adduct formation. On the basis of the data, a six-coordinate structure about tin atom may tentatively be suggested for these compounds.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes*

Compd.**	Colour	Sn% : Found (Calcd.)	Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$
Bu ₂ SnCl(DNP)CNpy-3	Brown	20.4 (21.3)	0.7
Bu ₂ SnCl(DNP).CNpy-4	Yellow	20.8 (21.3)	–
Bu ₂ Sn(DNP) ₂ CNpy-3	Brown	16.7 (16.8)	–
Bu ₂ Sn(DNP) ₂ CNpy-4	Yellow	15.9 (16.8)	1.2
Ph ₃ Sn(DNP).phen	Green	19.0 (19.4)	–
Ph ₃ Sn(DNP).bipy	Brown	16.7 (17.2)	0.9
Me ₃ Sn(DNP).phen	Green	27.9 (27.8)	1.1
Me ₃ Sn(DNP).bipy	Brown	28.7 (29.5)	1.3

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

**DNP = 2,4-dinitrophenoxide ion.

In the IR spectra of organotin compounds with 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline, the bidentate mode of coordination to metal ion through both the nitrogen atoms

of the ligands has been indicated by the positive shift in $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{C=C}$ and ring stretching vibrations of the uncoordinated bases in agreement with the observations of previous workers⁵. The (C–H) out-of-plane deformation mode at $\sim 759\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in 2,2'-bipyridyl was observed as a weak band at $\sim 766\text{ cm}^{-1}$ upon complexation. On the other hand, the IR active bands at 852 and 837 cm^{-1} due to out-of-plane (C–H) deformation in 1,10-phenanthroline, moved to higher spectral region in its compounds.

The assignments of far-IR stretching vibrations have been carefully made by studying extensive literature reports for complexes formed with pyridines and related ligands⁶. The bands at 280–260 and $240\text{--}225\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these compounds have been attributed to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{Sn–C})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{Sn–C})$ modes, respectively⁷. It is important to mention here that the tin-nitrogen vibrations also occur at $\sim 280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ⁸ and are often coupled with other normal modes of vibrations of the same symmetry especially ring vibrations⁹, consequently, for the complexes studied herein, no straightforward assignments have been ascertained for $\nu(\text{Sn–N})$ modes. In case of adducts of $\text{Bu}_2^{\text{O}}\text{SnCl}\{\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4\}$, the bands at $\sim 375\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Sn–Cl}}$ mode^{2,8}. The $\nu_{\text{Sn–O}}$ vibrations were observed at $\sim 520\text{--}480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these complexes^{2,10}.

From the present observations in the absence of X-ray structural data, a plausible geometry around tin in complexes derived from 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline can not be assigned. It may however be assumed that these compounds exist in a heptacoordinate form, but the possibility of a hexacoordinate environment, resulting from a weak interaction between *ortho*-oxygen of NO_2 group of 2,4-dinitrophenoxide ion with metal or this donor being out of chelation can not be excluded. Hence, further spectroscopic studies are needed to deduce meaningful structural data for these complexes which are in progress. Nonetheless, the synthesis of such complexes may find interest from the standpoint of using them as biologically active compounds.

Experimental

Organotin(IV)-2,4-dinitrophenoxides of composition $[\text{R}_3\text{Sn}\{\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4\}]$ and $[\text{Bu}_2^{\text{O}}\text{SnCl}_{2-x}\{\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4\}_x]$ (R = Ph, Me; $x = 1$ and 2) were synthesized by the silver salt metathesis method reported earlier¹¹. Cyanopyridines (Aldrich) were crystallized from absolute ethanol and the purity was checked by m.p. and IR spectral data. 2,2'-Bipyridyl (Fluka) was crystallized from ethanol and then sublimed *in vacuo* prior to use. 1,10-Phenanthroline was made anhydrous by keeping it in an oven at low temperature and then dried over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator. THF was stored over CaH_2 and distilled over Na/K benzophenone under vacuum before use.

Tin was estimated gravimetrically as SnO_2 and chlorine by Volhard's method. C and H were analyzed on a Coleman CHN analyzer. Conductivity was measured in nitrobenzene (10^{-3} M solution) on an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge. The molecular weights were determined by Rast camphor method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet-Avatar 1000 FTIR spectrophotometer.

Preparation of complexes : To a solution of $[\text{R}_3\text{Sn}\{\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4\}]$ and $[\text{Bu}_2^{\text{O}}\text{SnCl}_{2-x}\{\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4\}_x]$ in THF (20 cm^3) was added a solution of nitrogenous bases, such as 3- and 4-cyanopyridines, 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline in THF taken in equimolar amounts in separate experiments. The reaction mixture was stirred for $\sim 10\text{ h}$ at room temperature ($25 \pm 1^\circ$). A slight change in the colour of the solution was observed during the course of the reaction. It was then reduced almost one-fourth of its original volume by evaporating the solvent under reduced pressure. The coloured solids that separated out were washed with petroleum ether and were dried under reduced pressure. Complexes of 2,2'-bipyridyl initially isolated as oil, were then transformed into powder after repeated treatment with petroleum ether. The 1 : 1 complexes were isolated regardless of the metal : ligand ratio.

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